

Poverty Prediction by Using Deep Learning on Satellite Images

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Abstract: As the universe finds it challenging to define poverty, the world bank views poverty as anyone living below \$2 per day. Government and international organizations are working to eradicate this poverty. The study reviews some research on satellite images on the prediction of poverty through the concept of CNN. The study split the datasets satellite images of four (4) countries: Nigeria, Mali, Malawi, and Ethiopia obtained from Kaggle in 90% for training with 15% of it for validation and 10% for testing. The datasets were analyzed using CNN, VGG16, ResNet50, which shows that the VGG16 model performs better than the other two models with the validation accuracy of 94%, while CNN has 91%. ResNet has the lowest validation accuracy of 62%. The rise of high-resolution satellite images that contain extensive data of regions or countries' patterns, features, and landscapes can be applied to determine the economic livelihood of people or nations. The application of satellite images to the prediction of poverty is much easier, faster, and less expensive compared to more the prediction becomes more accessible. This study recommends the need for the availability of large satellites images for every region or country. Future researchers should focus on satellite images to predict poverty and the application of satellite images in detecting crime, road traffic, agricultural soil, and the like.

Keywords: Convolutional Neural Network, Residual Network, Satellite Images, Architectural Neural Network, Support Vector Machine, Visual Geometry Group.

I. INTRODUCTION

The universe finds it difficult actually to define what poverty means. Some view it as a lack of essential things to make life comfortable, some percept it as hunger and lack of livelihood. Others see it as any group of people who lacks the basic amenities of life to live their lives, such as no access to school, shelter, food, healthcare services, water resources, etc. The World Bank refers to poverty as any person living below \$2 per day is regarded as a person living below poverty.

The African continent is categorized as the continent with the highest rate of people living below poverty. One of the features that cause poverty is the deficiency in good education. It elevates people to earn income, thus overflowing poverty. These are the reasons many countries budget large shares to go to education. Deficiency of jobs security or job growth is another prime cause of poverty because jobs security elevates people to access good incomes [2].

The availability of and accessibility to satellite imagery data proposes an exemplary quicker, less expensive, and riskless approach for collecting socio-economic information compared to the typical survey collection approach [3]. But currently, the technique architectural neural network (ANN) of machine learning combined with satellite imagery data have been the latest trends in quantifying economic livelihood status. This technology was due to the emergence of different algorithms models used to recreate from the machine learning communities.

The machine learning researchers use a convolutional neural network (CNN) to extract and detect feature patterns from day-to-day satellite images and apply these patterns to compute or quantify economic livelihood status. In 2015, Kaiming He et al. suggested a new network architecture known as residual neural network (ResNet). It is adopted due to its residual cognition to train deeper networks. And overshadow the challenges of decreased learning efficiency and incapability to increase the accuracy rate because of the deeper network depth [4,11].

Aim and Objectives

1. The prediction of poverty in Africa using satellite images is very significant when dealing with socio-economics to understand the level of people as evidence to apply for government social programs.
2. The technique can serve as a means of estimating poverty using satellite images from countries in Africa as data for development.
3. Hence, the result to be ascertained in this research study will provide increased algorithm results that can be credible and reliable for predicting the region's poverty and livelihood using satellite images.
4. The study will contribute to the algorithm's performance in the segmentation and prediction of poverty and livelihood in Africa will be found to be an increased algorithm compared to the existing tradition of the art of survey used for the same issues.

The availability of and accessibility to satellite imagery data proposes an exemplary quicker, less expensive, and riskless approach for collecting socio-economic information compared to the typical survey collection approach [10]. But currently, the technique artificial neural network (ANN) of machine learning combined with satellite imagery data have been the latest trends in quantifying economic livelihood status. This technology was due to the emergence of different algorithms models used to recreate from the machine learning communities.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

With the help of satellite imagery data and datasets, the determination of population economic well-being status will be effective and efficient, especially when such information is needed urgently. As everyday research on architectural neural networks keeps attracting more research grants, we will be seeing the emergence of new models or algorithms to support the prediction of poverty using satellite imagery data.

Piaggese [2], in his work with his colleagues, investigated the economic livelihood prediction process in the urban ecosystem of two developed nations. They presented that the applied procedures for economic livelihood mapping in materials can also use low settings in this boundary. Categorically, they have precept that an algorithm pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset can elaborate on the target, an essential fraction of the variance with no adjust-tuning routine or proxies [2,5,13].

Pandey, Agarwal, and Krishnan [3] proposed a two-step method for estimating poverty in rural geo-regions of India from satellite imagery data. Firstly, they train a multi-task amply convolutional model to determine three developmental signs. The leading resource is the roof, source of nighttime lighting, and access to drinking water from satellite imagery. They observed that the multi-task amply convolutional model automatically understood symbolic features, like roads, settlements, agricultural lands, and water bodies. Secondly, they train a model to estimate the economic livelihood status (straightway indicator of poverty) using the first model's computed developmental parameter/value results [3,9].

Wu and Tan's article used Chongqing, China, to exemplify the application of the ResNet50 neural network model by analyzing it in geo-regional economic research. Numerous experiments reveal the impact of satellite imagery and machine learning [16]. Their approach outperforms the direct use of sunset/nightlight imagery data to predict economic status. Moreover, the 'Squeeze-and-Excitation' roof/blocks are added into the Resnet50 model. The outcomes are also improved, which displays that the module can better increase the execution of the model and extract pattern features that better represent the economic level of the geo-region [4, 11, 16].

(Yeh et al., 2020) deep learning method also perhaps best regarded as a way to enlarge rather than replace traditional survey efforts, as local training data can frequently further increase model performance, and because other key living well-being outcomes often measured in surveys such as how wealth is shared between households, or among families within rural areas are harder to obtain in imagery. Likewise, they could also use their method to measure other key outcomes, including consumption-based poverty metrics or other essential livelihoods directional such as health results [4, 11].

(Kondmann, Zhu., 2020) Results outline that pioneering approaches that map poverty from satellite images with deep learning may struggle to capture trends in economic development over time [5]. Thoroughly validating these results in other countries and with other imagery is necessary to communicate the robustness of this weakness [5, 12].

(Head et al., 2017) The research presents a preliminary evaluation of the globalization ability of satellite-based approaches for predicting human development after replicating past studies that reestablished the potential for such techniques to estimate asset worth based in Rwanda [6]. They explained that the same method could not be trivially interpreted into evaluating other “softer” development outcomes (like health outcomes and source to clean drinking water) with the same correctness in other countries (precisely like Haiti and Nepal) [6, 13].

Angelini and Colleagues' work advances their previous study into picture-based models of economic livelihood situations using satellite imagery. Their study outcomes for three African countries are similar to their earlier studies of three different African countries using high-resolution public imagery [17].

The work of Engstrom and his research partners [18] shows results that spatial and spectral patterns did adequately well on their own at elaborating economic livelihood, with adjusted R2 number starting from decimal 0.46 to 0.54. After all, they also discover the spatial autocorrelation in the framed procedural residuals, which shows that significant explanatory variables are reducing or absent from the models. But, it is not surprising, especially when considering the complicated nature of urban economic livelihood. It is more significant than an essential precursor and rise of the spatial set-up of on-the-ground objects [18, 6, 13].

Irvine, Wood, and McBee [19], in their analysis of some selected sub-Saharan African geo-regions, image-derived patterns provide essential data for estimating survey answers across a range of questions. The achievement is commonly most substantial with questions on infrastructure, like accessibility to electricity, clean water, shelter, healthcare service and, sewage disposal. Social behaviors can also involve questions, but they act only slightly greater than chance. Compared to their results from the earlier study conducted in Afghanistan, the achievement in this work is less compelling [19].

In the paper [20], Das, Chhabra, and Dubey viewed that 'from applying the first standard techniques of gathering data on paper, to using technology that was not yet really explored in this specific domain, the goal was usually alike: Reduction of Global Poverty. They outline that this can be performed only with a correct poverty map of the earth. Figuring observations from numerous researches, it is clear that satellite imagery information mixed with different approaches studied for this paper or otherwise looks like the best means by which the universe needs to move forward and solve this significant global problem. The accumulated solutions can be helpful in policy-making by policymakers to develop frameworks that can work actively at all classes or levels [20, 8].

From their World Bank publication, Engstrom, Hersh, and Newhouse [26] question how well economic livelihood status derived from satellite imagery predicts poverty and which position is most significant? They examine these questions using a research segment of 1,291 villages in Sri Lanka, connecting parameters of economic well-being level with features or patterns obtained from high-resolution satellite imagery.

Okaidat and study peers [27] regard that 'number one objective of sustainable development goal (SDG) is to overshadow poverty.' The scholars primarily outline procedures to recognize the spatial distribution of economic livelihood. The data that Okaidat and peers [27] used in their project contains three datasets that involve satellite images for three nations: Malawi, Ethiopia, and Nigeria. They used 30% of every dataset for testing and 70% for training. They also use 20% of the training set for validation.

They applied Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) classifier with particular architecture to classify or segment the satellite images of Malawi, Ethiopia, and Nigeria into three groups related to three countries with various poverty levels. Class 0 is correlatedly assigned to Ethiopia, with the lowest economic livelihood status; class 1 was connectedly set to Malawi with the intermediate financial position. And class 2 was correlatedly assigned to Nigeria with the highest economic livelihood status [27].

III. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

In terms of materials, satellite images have been generally used in various sectors, like classification and detection. But satellite image processing needs a more preprocessing approach than typical classification or detection, as satellite images mainly depend on the procedure used. Therefore, researchers, both academia and industries, are committed to developing

satellite image processing to maximize performance features like classification, preprocessing, detection and segmentation, etc.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN), the foundation of the Deep Learning (DL) algorithm, has been used in satellite images for almost/over a decade. Before DL emerged, researchers focused on using Support Vector Machines (SVM) and ensemble classifiers such as Random Forest (RF) for image classification and detection. The materials used for the study are all discussed in this chapter. But to highlight them for the study in terms of performing the poverty prediction using satellite images are ANN such as (CNN, ResNet50, and VGG16), satellite images, image processing techniques, and a vast number of published academic kinds of literature from recognized journals.

The machine learning approach is the effective methodology needed for transforming these enormous amounts of unstructured satellite images into organized predicted ground status. The study adopted satellite images and a machine learning approach tailored to predict poverty using satellite images. This approach can improve the excellent segmentation of land use, poverty status, forest cover, and population unit, thereby enabling decision-making and research studies. The study obtained huge algorithmic possessions in model training & testing, connecting to leading artificial neural networks, via algorithmic validations that get the opportunity that satellite pictures are snapped from a fixed length and seeing angle from and capture repeating features and objects.

The study method (s) or approaches and materials are to ascertain the research's goal, such as approaches/theoretical/simulation, which aim to outline data/results that can verify the hypotheses. A short explanation of the parameters or things to be measured, estimated, predicted, or something to do with it is described. The satellite images were run through machine learning algorithms using a python programming language. It took a lot of hours in running the algorithm. The satellite images consist of the four African countries Nigeria, Mali, Malawi, and Ethiopia.

A. Architecture Workflow

This is the application of satellite images and machine learning to remotely determine the poverty of a region or country. Satellite imagery gives new information on the socioeconomic status of wealth and poverty. Some study predicted poverty status using the satellite images were taken during the night used houses with electric lights as a household living above poverty, while places that do not have the electric light is categorized as houses living in the poverty.

The concept machine learning technique is the significant approach required for predicting these vast amounts of unorganized satellite images into organized predicted information indicating poverty status data. The study applied satellite images and a deep learning approach purposely to predict or estimate poverty status using satellite images. This approach can also improve the better segmentation of land use, poverty status, forest cover, and population unit, thereby enabling decision-making and research studies.

This study obtained huge algorithmic possessions in model training & testing, connecting to leading deep neural networks, through algorithmic validations that get the benefits that satellite images are snapped from a fixed length and seeing angle from and capture repeating features and objects. Through the innovation of deep learning, we have the means to predict poverty using satellite images. The traditional way of surveying to predict poverty involves going to house-to-house, household-to-household to get the necessary information to determine the poverty.

B. The Study Area and Context

The African continent is categorized as the continent with the highest rate of people living below poverty. The study participant countries are Nigeria, Malawi, Mali, and Malawi. One of the features that cause poverty is the deficiency in good education. It elevates people to earn income, thus overflowing poverty.

Dataset: The datasets were satellite images from [1] Kaggle website captured using satellite technology, as the details of the satellite pictures are shown in the table below. The images involve a large scale of information concerned with landscape patterns related to livelihood operation and recognize some main factors like the source of water, road, roof building, building, and farmlands. The image is in original pixels size of 256x256 Red Green Blue (RGB), i.e., color images. The datasets images are in four African countries: Malawi, Ethiopia, Mali, and Nigeria. Mali has 14,759 images, Ethiopia 8,590 images, Malawi 12,700 images, and Nigeria 11,551 images. Therefore, the total images of 47,600.

TABLE I. SHOWING THE TOTAL NUMBER OF IMAGES AND THEIR TRAINING AND TESTING SETS

Country	Number of Images			
	Training	Validation	Testing	Total
Ethiopia	90%	15% of train	10%	8,590
Malawi	90%	15% of train	10%	12,700
Mali	90%	15% of train	10%	14,759
Nigeria	90%	15% of train	10%	11,551
Total	Train % total	15%	10% total	47,600

Table I. The directory comprises two folders - training set and test set, each comprising four folders having images containing agriculture, buildings, roads, and water. Each image covers an area of approximately a 6km radius. The train-test split is 90:10%

C. Proposed Approach of the Study

Several approaches were available for the satellite image, but the classification approach was best suited for predicting poverty using satellite imagery. We have classification, transforming, and correction techniques. In proposed approach can provide qualitative and quantitative information cheaper than a typical survey. The proposed classification using the deep learning (CNN) approach plays a vital duty in exploiting, extracting, and transforming worthy information from vast satellite images.

Classifier: Convolutional Neural Network is applied to extract features such as edges, shapes, corners, and pixel intensities. The output of the trained CNN model will be one of the four classes – agriculture substances, building roof, road, water

Fig. 1 Showing CNN Classifier [8]

The study model is implemented in two pre-trained models (ResNet50, VGG16) and a developed CNN model from the beginning to classify/segment the high-resolution satellite pictures into four groups of classes as four ranks of poverty: very high, high, medium, and low poverty. Nigeria represents very high poverty status, Malawi represents low poverty status, Mali represents medium poverty, and Ethiopia represents intense poverty.

By feeding each model with the augmented images, then the CNNs algorithm will automatically understand to extract many features that recognize some primary factors. Such as roads, buildings, vegetation and & farmlands, water resources, and building roof, discover relatively image patterns and make predictions of the livelihood well-being or poverty level.

The data preprocessing techniques was with the help of the Keras library frame on top of TensorFlow using a python programming language. This technique allows for the easy execution of the architectural neural network, i.e., convolutional neural network (CNN) for image segmentation. The input layers accept in standard image size as already stated there rescaling regular of occurrence are divided by 255 across the dataset to make easy accessibility of the neural network. It has an import layer acceptable for RGB picture height, width, and depth. Eight (8) batch sizes were initialized as datasets generators' sizes. There was an adjustment of the size of the training set in adjusting the model overfitting and enhancing the generalization.

1. CNN

The study has eight (8) convolutional layers, two (2) connected layers, and an output layer with padding and the activation function. The first layer has 32 filters and a 3x3 canal size with padding. Then the layers were followed by the activation function used in all the convolution layers, ReLU. ReLU allows averting exponential growth in the prediction needed to execute the neural network. The second also has 32 filters with a 3x3 canal and batch normalization.

After the second convolutional layer, the study applied max pooling to reduce the specialized dimension of the previous layer's output, then a drop-out of 0.25 was applied as regularization. The third and fourth convolutional layer has 64 filters of 3x3 canal size with padding followed with batch normalization and max-pooling layer and a drop-out (the drop-out is just like the previous).

The fifth and sixth convolutional layer has 128 filters with a 3x3 canal size followed by batch normalization, max pooling, and drop out. The seventh and eighth convolutional layer has 256 filters with a 3x3 canal size followed by batch normalization, max-pooling layer, and drop out.

After the final 8th convolutional layer, the dense or fully-connected layer was passed to the fully connected layer.

The first and second dense layers have 1024 nodes, followed by activation function 'ReLU' and batch normalization, followed by a drop-out layer in the second dense or fully connected layer. The output or SoftMax layer has four nodes that indicate 'very high,' 'high,' 'medium,' and 'low.' The SoftMax function is applied for multiple class segmentation problems where group membership is needed more than one-two groups/class labels.

Experimentation:

Adam optimization $1e-4$ (0.0001) was also applied as the learning rate with the decay of $1e-4$. They are all optimized by the learning rate by the number of epochs defined. As the class was multiple groups, a categorical cross-entropy was applied since it is not in binary mode. Early stopping was initialized into the model to monitor overfitting, and image batch sizes of eight (8) were set as model generators. Both the train and validation images were passed to the network as generators.

2. VGG16

VGG16 is a pre-train CNN architecture that consists of 16 layers, and the input layer accepts an image's shape of $256 \times 256 \times 3$ and the weight of ImageNet. Then followed base pair of convolution layers with its average pooling size of 4×4 . Then flatten function, which serves for converting data into a one-dimensional array for accepting into the next layer—followed by 4096 dense or fully-connected layers with ReLU activation function with the drop-out of 0.5. Then the SoftMax activation function or/with output layer.

The concept of the VGG model is according to ANN with the can filter size 3×3 as the datasets are not that compatible with the VGG16 algorithm set. A fine-tuned concept was applied to the model by adjusting some layers as frozen and applying global average pooling layers to the architecture that assisted in revising the parameters. In trying to codify the VGG16 network to reduce overfitting, a dense of 4096 neurons and ReLU activation function was applied and 0.5 drop-outs. The multiclass function is four (4) from the four (4) neurons. That is the reason why the SoftMax was involved as an activation function.

Experimentation:

VGG16 is a pre-train CNN architecture that consists of 16 layers, and the total Epochs of 200 were applied with a learning rate set as $1e-4$ (0.001). Adam optimization $1e-4$ was used as the learning rate with the decay of $1e-4$. All the optimization by the learning rate is divided by the total number of epochs defined. The epoch was reduced to 100 during the experiment but was stopped at 16 epochs. The early stopping technique was initialized into the model to monitor overfitting, and image batch sizes of eight (8) were set as model generators. The VGG network training continues from 96 epochs to 100. As the class was multiple groups, a categorical cross-entropy was applied since it is not in binary mode. Hyperparameters rates for every network model were regarded as the same technique. Both the train and validation images were passed to the network as generators.

3. RESNET50

ResNet50 architecture is on the style on large arranged in stacked residual quantity and applies a jump connection approach to resolve the disappearing/destroying gradient challenge. Fully named residual network 50 was initialized using the shape 256×256 using 3×3 canal filters layer as size. The convolutional average pooling size of 7×7 was initiated, followed by

flattening, which is used to transform the data into a one-dimensional array for inserting it into the following layer. Then fully connected or dense layer of 4096 with ReLU activation function. They were followed by the drop-out of 0.5, Then a dense or fully-connected layer of 2048 with ReLU activation function with the drop-out of 0.5, followed by 1024 dense layer with ReLU activation function with the drop-out of 0.5, then the fully connected or dense SoftMax activation function.

Experimentation:

Epochs of 200 were initialized with the learning rate of $1e-4$ (0.0001), Adam optimization with learning and decay of $1e-4$ are divided by the epochs defined. The callback monitors were used then adjusted the learning rate by remaking it $1e-5$ (0.00001). Also, the same with the learning rate and the decay rate is divided by the epochs defined. Categorical cross-entropy was applied to maintain the multiple class. The model was trained using 200 epochs, and the early stopping method was used; as a result, the Resnet50 model stopped after executing 59 epochs.

Fig. 2 Showing CNN satellite image and survey Procedure

TABLE II. SHOWING THE MODELS PARAMETERS

Hyper-Parameters	Models		
	CNN	VGG16	ResNet50
Learning-Rate	$1e-4$	$1e-4$	$1e-4$
Drop-out	0.5	0.5	0.5
Hidden-layer activation function	RELU	RELU	RELU
Output-layer activation layer	SoftMax	SoftMax	SoftMax
Epochs	200	200	200
Size of batch in training	8	8	8
Size of batch for validation	8	8	8

Table II. above shows the applied parameters while running the algorithm or model from the learning rate, drop-out, hidden layer, output layer, activation function, etc.

IV. FINDINGS

Finding is the chapter that displays the result of the study by showing any findings or result from the work and development activity that can be initiated or improved product, design, process, invention, innovation, and advancement in any procedure, approach, methodology, technique, apparatus or the machine.

The multi-class classification of the study was done using the three models, namely CNN, ResNet, and VGG16.

Figure3 shows the results that CNN linear model does okay on the training data with 91% accuracy as the accuracy from validation is 71%. The training and validation accuracies are shown in the Figures below.

Fig. 3 Showing the performance of CNN model loss and accuracy.

The training loss curves are down while the validation loss is inverse to the training loss in the CNN model, as shown in Figure 3.

In terms of VGG16 shown in figure 4, the training accuracy of 94%, while its validation accuracy is 86%. The training and validation accuracies are shown in the Figures below.

Fig. 4 Showing the performance of VGG16 model loss and accuracy.

The VGG16 also has variations between the training and validation losses, as shown in Figure 4 above.

The ResNet50 model in figure 5 shows that the training accuracy is 62% while its validation accuracy of 58%. The training and validation accuracies are shown in the Figures below.

Training Loss and Accuracy on Satellite Images for Poverty Prediction

Fig. 5 Showing the performance of ResNet model loss and accuracy.

The ResNet50 model shows that the training and validation losses are on a closed curve, as shown in Figure 5.

TABLE III. SHOWING THE CNN MODEL RESULTS

Countries	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Nigeria	0.70	0.72	0.71	1154
Mali	0.83	0.64	0.72	1475
Malawi	0.74	0.82	0.78	1270
Ethiopia	0.75	0.83	0.79	1717
Accuracy			0.75	5616
Macro Average	0.76	0.75	0.75	5616
Weighted Average	0.76	0.75	0.75	5616

Table III. represent that the CNN model performs averagely well with an accuracy of 0.75. It also shows that Ethiopia has the highest F1 score while Nigeria has the lowest, with 0.71. CNN performance is better than the ResNet model.

TABLE IV. SHOWING THE VGG16 MODEL RESULTS

Countries	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Nigeria	0.87	0.77	0.82	1154
Mali	0.81	0.91	0.86	1475
Malawi	0.88	0.88	0.88	1270
Ethiopia	0.93	0.92	0.92	1717
Accuracy			0.87	5616
Macro Average	0.87	0.87	0.87	5616
Weighted Average	0.88	0.87	0.87	5616

The above Table IV. shows that the VGG16 has a performance accuracy of 0.87 which means it performs better than the two models. The country with the lowest F1-score of 0.82 while the country with the highest F1-score of 0.92. The table shows that the VGG16 model performs better than all other models.

TABLE V. SHOWING THE RESNET MODEL RESULTS

Countries	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Nigeria	0.53	0.59	0.56	1154
Mali	0.64	0.65	0.64	1475
Malawi	0.56	0.59	0.57	1270
Ethiopia	0.74	0.66	0.70	1717
Accuracy			0.62	5616
Macro Average	0.62	0.62	0.62	5616
Weighted Average	0.63	0.62	0.63	5616

The above Table V shows that the ResNet performed weak with an accuracy of 0.62. ResNet from the previous work of other authors shows that the model is not suitable for such kind of analysis.

These **weighted average** were determined by multiplying every patterns prediction by the algorithm's model weight to produce the weighted total, then by dividing the value by the sum of the weights. The **macro average** was calculated straightforward using the normal averaging methods. The macro average F1 score is determined using the arithmetic mean (sometimes known as unweighted mean) of all the per class F1 scores. The countries were classified where zero was assigned to Malawi as a country with the lowest economic status, one was assigned to Mali as a country with a medium economic status, two was assigned to Ethiopia as the country with the high economic status, while three was assigned to Nigeria as the country with the very high economic status. The classification was applied using the convolutional neural network, one of the vital models of deep learning techniques.

V. CONCLUSION

The idea of knowing the economic livelihood of people or region by government, international organization, or non-governmental organization to make policy or decision that uplift the living standard status of the people. The manual survey of going house to house, household to household in either the rural or urban areas, is time-consuming and expensive. The rise of high-resolution satellite images that contain extensive data of regions or countries' patterns, features, and landscapes can be applied to determine the economic livelihood of people or nations.

The application of satellite images to predict poverty is much easier, faster, and less expensive than the conventional survey. The study deploys datasets from the website Kaggle with a 5.2 GB size that contain images of 4 countries: Nigeria, Mali, Malawi, and Ethiopia. The datasets were split into 90% for training sets and 10% for testing sets, then 15% of training sets were applied for validation.

The countries were classified where zero was assigned to Malawi as a country with the lowest economic status, one was assigned to Mali as a country with a medium economic status, two was assigned to Ethiopia as the country with the high economic status, while three was assigned to Nigeria as the country with the very high economic status. The classification was applied using the convolutional neural network, one of the vital models of deep learning techniques.

The CNN model performs averagely with a percentage of 75%, which shows that it is better than ResNet. The VGG16 model was the model that performs best compared to the CNN and ResNet, with an accurate performance of 87%. While the ResNet was the model with the lowest version of 62% compared to the other two models. The VGG16 was the best model with the highest performance, CNN with medium performance, and ResNet was the lowest performance.

The idea of deep learning is not just coming to stay to be solving our modern-day problems only, but it keeps on increasing in terms of its capacity as a lot of funds have been invested in its research and development every day. This study combined the latest conventional survey of the four African countries, Nigeria, Mali, Malawi, Ethiopia, and the high-resolution satellite images of the same countries.

The results of this study [28] raise a host of issues for further research and put up an ongoing debate concerning the application of predictive or estimative approaches in public policy (Athey & Imbens, 2017). One of the most nearly of these issues is the debate of whether high-resolution satellite indexes can replace with census data in a variation context and for several indexes.

There is no assurance that the estimative or predictive capacity of developing density, shadows, and other pattern features recorded will hold in all ecosystems. Another line of research may explain whether we can apply modifications in high-resolution satellite imagery to estimate or predict changes in economic livelihood status of well-being towards space and

time. Economic Livelihood (poverty) surveys are gathered using traditional means every three years, and the most current general predictions are generated with a three-year latency.

Therefore, the capability to “now-cast” computation of economic livelihood well-being status by often adding the latest modified high-resolution satellite images with the most current traditional survey-based estimation of economic livelihood (poverty) has strong potential. Another future research that can clear doubt on recognizing the excellent means to determine into adjacent geographical areas or regions that have not been dealt with by surveys.

Globally, the unavoidable improvements in the availability of high-resolution images and pattern feature recognition models, in connection with the motivating outcomes from this study, reflects that high-resolution satellite images will turn into a worthier tool to assist governmental, non-governmental organizations, and other stakeholders better to know the spatial nature of economic livelihood poverty.

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